

Tool 12

Citizen Science tools

Welcome to the Citizen Science Starter Kit.

This template is part of Module 4 “Getting started with citizen science” (phase 2 – develop), which gives you a first overview of often used citizen science tools for data collection, analysis, visualisation, and sharing.

The selected tools are applicable to the European context, and freely available unless mentioned otherwise. Platforms, apps, or sensors that are project specific, and thus not reusable, were not included in this list.

If you have any further questions about this template, please contact citizenscience@vub.be.

1. Citizen science platforms

- **Zooniverse:** The [Zooniverse](#) is an international platform for the annotation and transcription of data sets, and counts more than one million interested citizen scientists worldwide. If you would like to run your project on Zooniverse, you will have to apply to the platform. In the project builder section, you can upload your data sets (images, sounds, etc.) and choose the tasks you want the volunteers to do (e.g. annotating images, classification, labelling, etc.).
- **CitSci:** [CitSci](#) is a web and mobile platform for data collection and visualization. You can create your own project space, similar to Zooniverse. The platform offers analysis options through basic summary statistics, and visualizes data with maps, bar charts, etc.
- **CS logger & project builder:** These [tools](#) are developed by the Citizen Science Centre Zurich. The CS logger helps you to set up a data collection project through a mobile app. People can contribute in multiple forms of digital data (e.g. text, images, video, etc.). Once the data is collected, the project builder helps you with the analysis (e.g. image analysis, pattern recognition, text transcription, etc.).
- **DoeDat:** [DoeDat \(Dolt\)](#) is the online crowd sourcing platform of the Meise Botanical Gardens (Belgium), on which citizens can digitise their herbaria. The purpose of this crowdsourcing platform is to help the Meise Botanical Gardens to digitize their collections and to give citizens the chance to play an active part in this process. You can also post your project on the ‘DoeDat’ platform if it fits within the themes of the platform. The platform offers features to transcribe text and to categorize images.

- **‘Vele Handen’:** [Vele Handen \(Many Hands\)](#) engages citizen scientists in the transcription of historical, often handwritten, documents. ‘VeleHanden’ is a crowdsourcing platform of Picturae. Picturae is a Dutch enterprise active in digitizing and opening up heritage collections for museums, archives and libraries at home and abroad.
- **Spotteron:** [Spotteron](#) is a paid citizen science toolkit with custom-made mobile applications and web interfaces for your project. The tools offer a wide range of features for data management, including data analysis and visualisation, as well as community features.
- A similar tool is **Coreo:** [Coreo](#) is a platform that enables you to build your own data collection apps.
- **Pybossa:** [Pybossa](#) is a freely accessible crowdsourcing platform for the development of platforms and data collection of online projects in which volunteers can take part.
- **Maptionnaire:** [Maptionnaire](#) is a paid citizen science platform for collecting local insights and analysing GIS-based data. There are various analysis and visualization options, as well as community features.
- **Maplix:** [Maplix](#) specializes in digital citizen participation and provides map-based tools to collect spatial input from citizens. They also have a paying service.
- **COESO VERA Hub:** [VERA](#) stands for **V**irtual **E**cosystem for **R**esearch **A**ctivation. It’s an online hub where researchers and “engaged stakeholders” (organizations and community leaders who coordinate directly with local citizens) gather together and co-create participatory research projects within the social sciences and humanities disciplines. On the hub, VERA users create their profiles to find each other, create project spaces with access to helpful tools for collaboration, and search for funding.
- **Agouti:** [Agouti](#) is a platform for projects using wildlife cameras with built-in image analysis tools. It lets camera trappers organize surveys, efficiently process images, obtain standardized output of the results, and safely archive their data.

2. Mobile applications

- **ObsIdentify:** [ObsIdentify](#) allows users to take pictures of organisms, such as plants, animals and fungi, which the application then automatically recognizes and adds to the [waarnemingen.be](#) database.
- **CyberTracker:** [Cybertracker](#) is a tool to create smartphone apps for field data collection and data visualization, free of charge. It is being used worldwide by indigenous communities, in protected areas, for scientific research.
- **eBird:** [eBird](#) is managed by the Cornell Lab of Ornithology. This biodiversity-related citizen science project/database receives more than 100 million bird sightings each year. Observations are entered in a species map, from which you can explore hotspots and compare totals.
- **BirdNET Sound ID:** [BirdNet](#) is another app developed by the Cornell Lab of Ornithology, together with the Chair of Media Informatics at Chemnitz University of Technology. It is a research platform that aims at recognizing birds by sound at scale. It serves as a citizen science platform and offers analysis software for extremely large collections of audio. (A third and similar app by the Cornell Lab or Ornithology is [the Merlin app](#).)
- **iNaturalist:** [iNaturalist](#) is an international application and online community through which citizens help identify plants and animals. You download a mobile application, you take a picture via the application, and you upload it to the community. The Dutch variant of this platform is <https://waarnemingen.be/> or Natuurpunt, Natagora and Stichting Natuurinformatie. Here, you also download a mobile application to upload your observation. Automatic image recognition helps to identify the species or animal.
- **OdourCollect:** [OdourCollect](#) is a free application that any citizen can use to report odours and plot them on a map. This mobile application was developed by the D-NOSSES project.
- **EASIN Invasive Species in Europe App:** the “Invasive [Alien Species Europe](#)” App allows citizens to report sightings of invasive alien species of Union Concern, and to create new surveys and projects for reporting observations.
- **Pl@ntNet:** [Pl@ntNet](#) is a tool to help to identify plants with pictures. It’s available as a mobile and web application and currently hosts 22 projects.
- **WeObserve Toolkit:** This [toolkit](#) includes a wide range of open access tools that new and existing citizen science projects can use to assist their activities. The section on Training & Data Collection for environmental monitoring includes tools that support data collection for a range of environmental and geographical dimensions.

3. Sensors

- **Smart Flanders / best buying model:** An [inventory](#) of the best low-budget sensors for citizen science was made by PWC, in the context of the Smart Flanders programme 2020-2021. The inventory (Dutch only) focusses on sensors in environmental monitoring, mobility, health, etc., and lists its main characteristics and price.
- **Air quality sensors / VAQUUMS:** the [VAQUUMS project](#) aims to determine air quality levels through innovative measuring techniques. On their website, a list of air quality sensors is listed for PM10, PM2.5, O₃ and NO₂ together with test results. The prices are mentioned on their website.
- **Air quality sensors / sensor.community:** The [sensor.community](#), a civic tech network, offer a range of do-it-yourself sensing kits for air quality and noise. They publish the data from the sensors through an open API. A sensor kit starts from 55 euros.
- **'Together for Clean Air'** ('Samen voor zuivere lucht'): this website is available in many languages and provides, among others, [an overview](#) of different air pollutants and the best ways to measure them. They also have [a data portal](#) which shows measurements on a map.
- **Traffic counter / "Telraam":** The Telraam sensor continuously monitors a street from a citizen's window, providing crucial data on various modes of transport, including motorized vehicles, cyclists, pedestrians, and more. Through the Telraam API you can retrieve all traffic data under an open data, non-commercial license. The prices per device are listed on [their website](#).
- **senseBOX:** [SenseBox](#) is used in digital education, citizen science and professional environmental data collection. The basis is a microcontroller that can be connected with many sensors. The data is visualized in openSenseMap.
- **iSPEX:** The [iSPEX tool](#), developed by the company Pocket Science, helps to measure water and air quality through a smartphone spectrometer and polarimeter.

4. Analyse and visualise data

Some of the above platforms and mobile applications offer in-built analysis and visualisation options. You can also try these specialized tools for analysing and visualising data:

- **Tableau:** [Tableau](#) is a paid visual analytics platform to explore and manage data, and to share insights.
- **Shiny:** [Shiny](#) is a free web app for data science. It allows creation of a basic platform whereby users can interact with your data through R or Python.
- **Canva:** Through [canva](#) you can create infographics, graphs and charts through pre-build templates to present and share your results. Free and paid versions are available.
- **Padlet:** With [Padlet](#) you can create beautiful boards to collect, organise and present your data in a collaborative way. Similar tools are [Mural](#), [Miro](#), Google [Jamboard](#) and [Wooclap](#) (which offers both a free version and paid services).
- **ArcGIS StoryMaps:** With [ArcGIS StoryMaps](#) you can transform your GIS-based maps into digital stories. It is a paid platform.
- **GitHub repository:** On this [page](#) you can find a curated list of open software and other resources for analysis and visualisation, and many other tools.
- **WeObserve Toolkit:** This [toolkit](#) includes a wide range of open access tools that new and existing citizen science projects can use to assist their activities. The section on Data Quality and visualization includes tools to help with all aspects of citizen-generated data management, including validation, analysis, quality assurance and visualization.

5. Share or find open data

- **Biodiversity data / GBIF:** The Global Biodiversity Information Facility ([GBIF](#)) is an international network and research infrastructure aimed at making scientific data on biodiversity available to anyone, and accessible and searchable through a single portal.
- **Registry of Research Data Repositories:** [re3data](#) is a global registry of research data repositories that covers research data repositories from different academic disciplines.
- **Geopunt Vlaanderen:** You can share geo data from your citizen science project through [Geopunt-Vlaanderen](#), where you can also find a large number of open data. If you do not have any spatial data, then you can link the dataset through the [metadata portal](#) of Digitaal Vlaanderen.
- **Meemo:** For data about arts and heritage, you can check out the [Meemo platform](#) of the Flemish Institute for Archives.
- **Cos4Cloud Services:** The [Cos4Cloud](#) project developed 13 cutting-edge technologies to improve the interoperability, networking, data quality and secure management of data in citizen science.
- **OpenStreetMap:** [OpenStreetMap](#) is a free editable map of the world that aggregates user-generated data with open data.
- **GeoODK:** [GeoODK](#) is an open-source platform for projects working with GIS information. Geographic data can be collected, edited and visualized via apps.
- **Weather Observation Website:** WOW is a web application where professional and amateur meteorologists can share observations from their private weather stations. [This](#) is the Belgian website, but the initiative is international (cf. The European Meteorological Society's [website](#)).
- **Scivil's Data Charter:** [this charter](#) contains references to the following portals:
 - [ICOS Data Portal](#): provides observational data and [elaborated products](#) on greenhouse gases
 - [WoRMS](#): the World Register of Marine Species
 - [GenBank](#): this genetic sequence database contains an annotated collection of all publicly available DNA sequences
 - [Terrascope](#): here you'll find open source satellite images